

A federated paradigm of real-world data sources utilization for the empowerment of diagnosis, prognosis, and risk assessment of cardiovascular conditions

D2.1 CVDLINK User Requirements, Gaps and Challenges

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Project Summary

In the EU, more than 6 million new cardiovascular disease (CVD) cases and 1.8 million deaths are reported yearly, imposing a substantial burden on national healthcare systems and society in general. The development of effective preventive interventions, adapted for each individual and population, will reduce the overall cost of patient management and justify the assertion that CVDs can be prevented and controlled. The exploration of existing clinical, genetic, and real-world data sources can contribute to these goals. However, several challenges related to data availability, management, and processing complicate this process. The 48-month CVDLINK project aims to tackle these challenges by implementing a privacy-by-design European-wide federated platform-as-a-service (PaaS) to deliver effective data-driven human-centric interventions and advance research and management in the CVD domain. CVDLINK is based on two major offerings: (1) the seamless and legally compliant integration, secure sharing, and automated curation of existing data, and (2) a set of AI and data-enabled precision medicine tools and pipelines for better diagnosis, risk stratification, and treatment of CVDs. The project will examine seven different cardiovascular conditions, making use of retrospective datasets, cohort studies, and biobanks from seven countries, aiming to demonstrate how heterogeneous data sources can be effectively exploited to build comprehensive and trustworthy AI-driven tools to benefit health systems, patients, industry, and EU citizens. The developed tools will be validated in five countries, demonstrating the impact of the CVDLINK outputs. Additionally, the project will generate a set of best practices which, alongside a cost-effectiveness analysis and awareness-raising campaigns, will promote the adoption of CVDLINK outputs in the mid-term.

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Executive Summary

The aim of this report is to provide an early assessment of user requirements, challenges, pathways, pain-points, and an initial definition of business processes related to the CVDLINK federated AI-based cardiovascular risk assessment platform.

To elicit user requirements while also providing a broader understanding of the current practices and challenges in the cardiovascular domain, a questionnaire was drafted and shared with the international cardiovascular community. Also, co-creation and participatory design workshops were conducted with CVDLINK stakeholders to prioritize the needs of each stakeholder group (clinical partners, healthcare professionals, industry, academia). Early insights and user considerations were contextualized in desk research about the social and cultural aspects of the cardiovascular domain and then formalized in scenarios of use.

Security requirements and data interoperability are also considered part of the current report as CVDLINK is a data-driven project and it is of utmost importance that the CVDLINK system fulfils all the security requirements set by the data holder organizations to allow their data to become part of the CVDLINK federated system.

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List of Acronyms/Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BP	Business Process
CDM	Common Data Model
CVD	Cardiovascular Disease
CSC	Tampere University and Finnish IT Center for Science
CSV	Comma-separated values
CT	Computed tomography
DoA	Description of the Action (annex 1 of the CVDLINK grant agreement)
ECG	Electrocardiogram
EDF	European Data Format
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Records
ER	Emergency Room
EU	European Union
EWS	Early Warning Score
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDF	Geographic Data File
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Practitioner
HD	Haemodialysis
ICD-10	International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision
MACE	Major Adverse Cardiovascular Events
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership

List of Partners

Abbreviation	Beneficiary	Country
SIM	SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL (Coordinator)	Romania
VICOM	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	Spain
TAU	TAMPEREEN KORKEAKOULUSAATIO SR	Finland
AUTH	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	Greece
TAUH	PIRKANMAAN HYVINVOINTIALUE	Finland
TRI	TRILATERAL RESEARCH LIMITED	Ireland
TUDa	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT DARMSTADT	Germany
VER	VERACELL OY	Finland
AMC	IATRIKO ATHINON EMPORIKI ANONYMOS ETAIREIA	Greece
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	Greece
HYMC	MEDICAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION DEVELOPMENT OF INFRASTRUCTURE AND HEALTH SERVICES NEAR HILLEL YAFFE MEDICAL CENTER	Israel
KIHDL	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	Israel
UHAM	UNIVERSITAET HAMBURG	Germany
UMFCD	UNIVERSITATEA DE MEDICINA SI FARMACIE CAROL DAVILA DIN BUCURESTI	Romania
IMSP	INSTITUTIA MEDICO-SANITARA PUBLICA 'INSTITUTUL DE CARDIOLOGIE' IN PROCES DE REORGANIZARE	Moldova
WCS	WELLICS EFARMOGES EREVNAS KAI PLIROFORIKIS MONOPROSOPI I.K.E.	Greece
KTU	KAUNO TECHNOLOGIJOS UNIVERSITETAS	Lithuania
UTARTU	TARTU ÜLIKOOL	Estonia
SYNYO	SYNYO GmbH	Austria

1 Introduction

The aim of this report is to provide an early assessment of user requirements, challenges, pathways, pain-points, and initial definition of business processes related to the CVDLINK federated AI-based cardiovascular risk assessment platform.

1.1 Scope and Objectives

This is the first of two deliverables reporting the activities and findings from Work Package 2 “Landscape analysis, data sharing and integration challenges and system design”.

This deliverable reports the outcomes of task T2.1 “Challenges and gaps in current pathways”, and intermediate results of tasks T2.2 “Analysis of socio-cultural contexts”, T2.3 “Co-creation workshops and participatory design”, T2.4 “Data interoperability and security requirements”, and T2.5 “Scenarios of use definition” that will continue after the delivery of this deliverable at M12.

The objectives of WP2 include:

- 1) the analysis of user requirements and challenges considering socio-economic views and established healthcare processes regarding data sharing and integration, as well as the application of AI tools for the management of cardiovascular cases
- 2) the structured incorporation of the users’ involvement in the design process, allowing a preliminary validation of CVDLINK concepts
- 3) the analysis of system requirements for the development and deployment of the CVDLINK platform
- 4) the definition of scenarios of use, considering the user journeys and identified pain-points
- 5) the generation of a scalable and modular system design that will facilitate the foreseen technical activities and support future deployments and integrations.

The deliverable D2.2 that is to be delivered by M18 of the project will report the user requirement work continued after the submission of the present deliverable and expand to cover the technical requirements derived partially from the user requirements identified in this document.

1.2 Structure of the Report

Methods used and activities performed in the different tasks reported in the deliverable are presented under Section 2 “Approaches to user requirements”. Section 3 “Results on User Requirements Elicitation” presents the results of the conducted activities and Section 4 “Conclusions” sums up the findings reported in the deliverable.

2 Approaches to User Requirements

The approach proposed to elicit user requirements and identify potential gaps and challenges is based on a questionnaire distributed to the healthcare professionals and cardiologists involved in the CVDLINK project. The CVDLINK questionnaire was also shared publicly and all project partners distributed it to local cardiology hospitals and communities. The results assessed and included in the current report are based on the answers received by 3rd of November 2024, after which the questionnaire was closed.

Also, co-creation and participatory design workshops were conducted to clarify the needs of different CVDLINK stakeholder groups like clinical partners, healthcare professionals, industry, and academia.

Next, the outcomes of these formal assessments were consolidated in the form of scenarios of use alongside security considerations. The results of all these approaches were finally formalized in a high-level list of user requirements. Figure 1 illustrates the process of obtaining the user requirements. In the subsections below, details for all the proposed approaches are provided, alongside with country specificities.

Figure 1. Research approaches to elicit user requirements

2.1 Questionnaire for Cardiovascular Healthcare Professionals

A questionnaire targeting cardiovascular healthcare professionals was designed by medical experts from Hillel Yaffe Medical Center, Israel and other CVDLINK consortium partners, considering the specific objectives of two WP2 tasks: T2.1 “Challenges and gaps in current pathways” and T2.2 “Analysis of socio-cultural contexts”. The [“EU Survey”](#) tool was selected as the platform for sharing the questionnaire online and collecting the results.

The aim of the proposed questionnaire was to collect data from healthcare professionals about cardiovascular risk factors and the opportunity to use the latest technologies (e.g., AI tools) to assess cardiovascular risk and facilitate a quick diagnosis.

2.1.1 Description of the Development of the Questions

A stepwise approach was followed to design the CVDLINK questionnaire for cardiovascular healthcare professionals. The task leader (HYMC) initiated the development with a draft list of questions that was discussed during several WP2 meetings, and all project partners had the opportunity to review, comment, and suggest modifications.

The primary objective of these discussions was to design a comprehensive and targeted questionnaire that could uncover critical insights from healthcare professionals regarding their practices, challenges, and perspectives in cardiovascular care.

The development process began with identifying key thematic areas and research objectives. The core topics, that the questionnaire would address, were systematically and collectively determined. This included discussions on clinical practices, patient care approaches, technological adoption, and knowledge gaps in cardiovascular disease management. Emphasis was placed on ensuring that the questionnaire was both scientifically robust and user-friendly, enabling respondents to provide meaningful and accurate information efficiently.

The questionnaire was anonymous to avoid processing personal data. The final set of questions was uploaded and published in “EU Survey” by HYMC. TRI assisted in formulating the participant information leaflet that was shown to the participants along with the questionnaire.

Recognizing the diversity of healthcare systems, cultural nuances, and legal frameworks across the participating countries, the design phase incorporated input from representatives familiar with these regional variations. Ethical considerations also played a central role, guiding the inclusion of topics and ensuring compliance with the ethical standards and legal requirements of each country. Particular attention was given to issues such as patient confidentiality, informed consent, and the responsible use of data.

2.1.2 Distribution of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire was distributed in various medical centres reaching healthcare professionals, mainly clinicians and nurses around Europe and Israel. The consortium members distributed the survey link using their own networks.

The finalized questionnaire was disseminated among partner organizations and their networks, each of which took responsibility for its distribution within their respective regions, by email or via their social networks. The distribution strategy was tailored to address the unique needs and characteristics of each country, ensuring accessibility and relevance to local healthcare professionals who work with CVD patients. Strategies included translating the questionnaire into local languages where necessary, adapting its content to align with regional practices, and employing appropriate communication channels to maximize reach and engagement.

Furthermore, each partner organization ensured compliance with their local regulatory frameworks. This involved consulting with legal and ethical committees and obtaining necessary approvals (if and when needed). Continuous feedback mechanisms were established to address any issues that arose during the distribution and data collection phases, promoting an adaptive and responsive approach.

This collaborative effort culminated in the successful collection of data from healthcare professionals across diverse regions, providing invaluable insights into cardiovascular care practices. The findings from this research are expected to contribute significantly to understanding current challenges and shaping future strategies for improving cardiovascular disease management. The process of distribution of the questionnaire is further described in Appendix 6.1.

2.2 Co-creation Workshops and Participatory Design

In addition to the questionnaire described in the previous section, co-creation workshops were arranged to further discuss the topics and issues identified. The workshops belong to Task 2.3 of CVDLINK. So far three workshops with end users and consortium members have been arranged. Task 2.3 will continue until M18, and the plan is to arrange at least one more workshop, potentially with researchers in Tampere University, Finland.

2.2.1 Workshop 1 with Clinical Partners of the Consortium

The first workshop took place in Tampere, Finland during the face-to-face project meeting on June 27th, 2024. Especially meeting participants working in clinical medicine were asked to take part in the workshop. The method for this workshop was a so-called starbursting-method with slight modifications. The aim was to first come up with multiple questions regarding the final CVDLINK risk assessment tool used in health care. The participants were divided in 5 small groups. The groups wrote their questions on the interactive Flinga-website shown in Figure 2, where they were all collected and saved for later use.

Figure 2. Overall scene of the Flinga website and the starbursting method.

Attendees were asked to write down questions beginning with the words how, when, what, who, why and where. After working in smaller groups, all workshop attendees discussed together about selected questions, listed in Appendix 6.1.

2.2.2. Workshop 2 with Healthcare Professionals in Tampere Heart Hospital

In Tampere Finland, healthcare workers from Tampere Heart Hospital were invited to take part in the workshop on October 22nd. A questionnaire similar to the one in the EU Survey system in Task 2.1 was distributed in the Tampere Heart Hospital with the added possibility to insert contact information. Approval to conduct this workshop in the Heart Hospital was obtained alongside the approval to distribute the questionnaire. Each attendee signed a separate consent form prior to taking part in the workshop.

Discussed topics were chosen based on the results of the first workshop and the questionnaire conducted in Task 2.1. Five attendees joined the workshop, four of whom had a nursing background and one of whom was a cardiologist. Discussion topics are elaborated in Table 3.

2.2.3 Workshop 3 – User Needs Identification

The third workshop took place in the third face-to-face meeting in Thessaloniki, Greece on 2.12.2024. All participants who attended the meeting participated in the workshop.

On-site participants formed seven groups, and one group was formed by the online participants. Because many of the topics discussed in the groups were touching clinical use cases of the CVDLINK system and related requirements, the groups were formed so that as many groups as possible had a clinician as a member.

Workshop organizers had earlier identified eight topics to be discussed in the groups and relevant questions related to these topics, which the participants tried to answer through discussion. Many of the topics were related to challenges identified through the questionnaire and in the prior workshops. The groups progressed through the list of topics trying to cover as many as possible. The discussion topics and related questions are listed in Appendix 6.4.

After the face-to-face workshop, the work continued online. The responses from each group were collected and discussed among task leaders. Results were summarized and analysed for further discussion. The summarized results are presented in Appendix 6.5. From the summary of results, frequent comments and identified user needs were chosen for prioritization. The needs were classified under six topics, each topic having from three to eight competing user needs.

An online meeting was organized on December 10th, 2024, and all consortium members were invited to join. During the meeting the participants individually prioritised the needs under the six categories using the anonymous voting tool of MS Teams. The results are presented in Section 0.

2.3 Desk Research on Data Sharing and Challenges

In addition to the analysis of attitudes towards data sharing, the impact of social and cultural differences on perceptions of data sharing, and general challenges in introducing and adapting AI technologies in healthcare based on the results of the questionnaire, scientific articles and national and EU-level reports were explored to collect more comprehensive insights on the topic.

Relevant articles and reports were searched using generative AI and a regular search engine (Google). Articles were appraised based on their title and abstract as well as their publication year due to the fast development of the AI and data-sharing domain. Approximately ten publications (articles or reports) were selected for detailed investigation and summarising. The summaries and analysis are presented in Section 3.1.3.

2.4 Data Interoperability and Security Requirements

Interoperability and security requirements were defined based on the results of the previous tasks of the project and external documents such as General Data Protection Regulation, European Health Data Space and EU AI Act:

Project-specific tasks:

The main source of project-specific requirements comes from user-defined tasks. Data providers represent the most security-sensitive segment of the CVDLINK platform's users. D1.2, the Data Management Plan (CVDLINK Consortium, 2024), provides the basis for addressing the needs of data providers in terms of data security. The requirements are complemented by the perspectives of another segment of users, namely researchers and clinicians. The results of T2.1 "Challenges and gaps in current pathways", T2.3 "Co-creation workshops and participatory design", and T2.5 "Scenarios of use definition" define the functional basis of the project that consist of an analysis of current challenges and gaps, sociocultural contexts, and definitions of scenarios of use. These results will form the basis for defining the interoperability and security requirements tailored to project goals.

European Union regulatory documents and initiatives

To ensure compliance with the standards defined by the EU regulations on healthcare data use and processing, the requirements defined in these documents will be used as the basis for this analysis. This also includes other EU initiatives that define the existing frameworks on healthcare data use and interoperability. The documents and initiatives analysed for this work are:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Council of the European Union , European Parliament, 2016) which establishes principles for lawful data processing, consent, and individual rights, ensuring robust protection of personal data.
- Data Protection by Design and by Default (by European Data Protection Board) (European Data Protection Board, 2020) which defines the integration of privacy and security into system design from the outset.
- European Health Data Space (EHDS) (EC-EUR-lex, 2022) is an initiative that promotes the secure and efficient sharing of health data across EU member states for healthcare, research, and policymaking.
- EU AI Act (European Commission, 2021) an EU regulatory framework for AI that ensures ensure better conditions for the development and use of AI.
- Interoperable Europe (European Commission, 2024) which aims to improve interoperability within EU by creating the setup and tools for interoperability within public administrations on a Union-wide scale and remove the unnecessary legal, organisational, semantical and technical obstacles.
- Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (Text with EEA relevance.) (European Comission, 2021)
- 1+ Million Genomes Initiative (European Commission, n.d.) is a project that defines the framework on improved disease prevention, allowing for more personalized treatments and supporting groundbreaking research.

- GenoMed4All initiative (European Union, n.d.) aims to transform the response to diseases using artificial Intelligence.

Other references not directly associated with EU initiatives:

Beyond EU-specific initiatives, the FAIR guiding principles of interoperability (European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, 2016) serve as a critical benchmark for ensuring the accessibility and usability of data across diverse platforms.

3 Results on User Requirements Elicitation

3.1 Analysis of User Requirements

Results from the questionnaire, the workshops, and the literature were first analysed separately and then jointly assessed to find the most important requirements.

3.1.1 Results of the International Questionnaire

A total of 223 survey responses were collected: 177 through the EU survey platform and 46 via the Tampere Heart Hospital survey. Most responses came from Romania (79), Israel (26), Finland (79), and Estonia (9). Unfortunately, participation from physicians in the Americas was limited, with only one response. As shown in Figure 3, below there are answers referring to multiple countries and answers mentioning two countries where the responders were active and affecting the sum of answers.

Figure 3. Geographical distribution of health facilities where responders were working

Table 1. Regional distribution of responders (multiple answers)

In which regions have you worked during the previous 5 years? (multiple answers)	Answer	Ratio
Eastern Europe	90	40.36%
Eastern Europe; Other	1	0.45%
Western Europe	12	5.38%
Western Europe; Middle East	1	0.45%
Western Europe; Eastern Europe	9	4.04%
Nordic Countries	80	35.87%
Middle East	24	10.76%
U.S.A	1	0.45%
U.S.A; Middle East	1	0.45%
Other	2	0.90%
No Answer	2	0.90%
Grand Total	223	100.00%

Regarding professional backgrounds, 168 respondents identified as physicians, while 49 were nurses and 6 did not provide this information.

Figure 4. Distribution of responders considering field of work

In terms of age distribution, 10 respondents were aged 18–25, 66 were aged 26–35, 67 were aged 36–45, 35 were aged 46–55, 44 were over 55, and 1 preferred not disclosing age.

Figure 5. Age distributions of responders

When asked about their trust in an AI-supported risk assessment tool on a scale of 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree), 15.25% selected 1, and 31.84% selected 2, indicating a generally positive attitude. Only 6.8% selected 5, while 45% of responders shared a degree of mistrust.

Figure 6. AI trust levels

Regarding the features needed to build trust in AI or machine learning-based risk stratification tools, the following preferences were highlighted:

Figure 7. AI/ML characteristics and trust level

Building trust is crucial for innovation and widespread adoption of AI tools and technologies. CVDLINK consortium assessed four characteristics that could improve the trust in AI/ML stratification tools. As shown in Figure 6 and Table 2. AI/ML characteristics and their values, there seems to be an agreement that development and operation of AI tools should be based on a large dataset.

Table 2. AI/ML characteristics and their values

	1 (strongly agree)	2	3	4	5 (strongly disagree)	No answer
Been based on a large dataset	122	39	18	11	28	5
Been based on clinically used parameters that are also part of the existing scores	98	56	24	17	22	6
Provides explanations related to the factors led to specific decisions	97	50	29	21	18	8

Been implemented by a well-known organization/ university/research institute	91	55	33	21	18	5
Been based on multi-site datasets	108	39	29	18	24	5

A key element for building trust when it comes to AI tools that was recognized by medical professionals refers to using and relying on clinically used parameters that are also part of calculating existing CVD risk scores: 70% (154 out of 223 responders) emphasized the importance of using clinically relevant parameters that align with existing risk scores.

Another factor that was considered very important by healthcare professionals was referring to clear explanations about the factors and disturbances that may affect the training of the AI models. Thus, 68% (147 responses) highlighted the need for clear explanations of the factors influencing specific decisions.

The reputation of the organisation building the AI tools and models has an important impact on whether healthcare professionals decide to use them. The questionnaire showed that 65% (146 of the responders) believed that the AI tool should be developed by a reputable organization.

Extrapolating the results and using datasets from multiple sites could be an important asset in building AI trust by detecting and correcting bias. 65% of CVDLINK responders preferred AI tools relying on multi-site datasets.

Overall, the findings suggest a positive attitude toward adopting AI-based risk assessment tools, provided they are developed using robust datasets, supported by reputable organizations, and capable of offering clear explanations for their decisions.

Furthermore, the findings show a list of factors that healthcare professionals rely on when assessing CVD risk and AI tools evaluation could stand for up to 35% of factors that could determine the CVD risk score.

Figure 8. Distribution of risk assessment factors

When analysing correlations, a slight trend was observed between younger respondents and greater openness to adopting AI-supported risk assessment tools; however, this trend lacked statistical significance. No significant correlations were found regarding profession, region of work, or perceived difficulty in making risk assessments.

3.1.2 Results from the Workshops

Workshop 1

Workshop 1 had approximately 15 participants from the consortium. Appendix 6.2 presents the questions relevant to CVDLINK system the break-out groups came up with in the first part of the workshop that was implemented using the Starburst approach and writing the resulting questions to a Flinga board. Figure 9 shows as an illustrative example the final Flinga board. Questions related to different question words (how, who, why,

where, what, when) are marked with different colours and arranged next to each other. The tags above and below the question tags and answers/opinions related to the questions picked up from the later discussion among the whole all workshop participants.

Figure 9. Illustration of the Flinga website and the questions by small groups.

Flinga platform allows participants to add their questions and comment on notes. All developed questions are listed in Appendix 6.2.

Groups came up with 45 different questions. Some of the questions were very specific, i.e. “how will the CVDLINK tool be accessed”, and some very general, i.e. “how reliable is this tool”.

Overall, participants still had partially different views on how the final CVDLINK tool could be used and who the main end users could be. Even though all questions could not be answered during this workshop, they had a role as thought awakening topics and conversation openers and were collected for later use.

From these 45 questions, one was selected as a discussion topic (nr. 12): *How will it [CVDLINK] change the daily work of cardiologists?* This topic raised a very active discussion that touched other questions as well. Appendix 6.3 presents the key themes from the discussion.

In conclusion, there were some varied views on how CVDLINK could be implemented in clinical use. **The importance of early detection and diagnosis was discussed**, which in practice means that **the CVDLINK system should be available for general practitioners and for nurses as well**. Often these professionals are the first to encounter a patient in healthcare, and after that they are referred to a specialist. GPs and nurses work as sort of gatekeepers when deciding on whether to consult a cardiologist or make treatment decisions independently. As a potential feature, **CVDLINK risk**

assessment could flag high risk patients and aid GPs or nurses in making consultations or taking certain tests. On the other hand, some participants had concerns about incorrect use of the tool in cases when the user doesn't have sufficient understanding in CVDs.

As for how CVDLINK would change the work of cardiologists, it was recognised that **reliable and accurate tools are needed**, and present risk assessment tools are often too general. **More personalised status from a patient with multiple parameters considered** could be achieved with CVDLINK. A new risk assessment tool might even add to cardiologists' workloads **if there are difficulties in its implementation to clinical use or if it requires a lot of manual work to upload patient data to the system.**

Workshop 2

The original aim was to invite cardiologists to discuss about the results from questionnaire T2.1 and the first workshop, focusing on the use of CVDLINK system in patient care, and to seek for requirements on data, user needs and challenges with them. Unfortunately, only one cardiologist was able to join this workshop. The other attendees had backgrounds in nursing.

Results of Workshop 2 support the findings of the T2.1 questionnaire, that nurses prefer to know the patient's status as is and use risk assessments such as early warning score (EWS) frequently. Nursing personnel usually doesn't take part in planning the patient's care in a way that a doctor does, regarding future tests, medication, conditioning, and so forth. This is why the emphasis in the discussion shifted towards using risk assessments such as EWS in patient care. This is reflected in the results detailed in Table 3. **For nursing personnel**, it is important that risk assessment tools are **easy, quick, and intuitive**, since oftentimes nurses must care for several patients at the same time. The ability of nurses to identify CVD symptoms varies, and with less experienced personnel or trainees, **a guiding system could help in decision-making.**

Table 3. Points raised in the discussion with workshop participants.

Recognized benefits for CVDLINK risk assessment	Risk assessment result based on the patient's own baseline, taking comorbidities and other background info into account
	Result based on patient's context, holistic approach
	Takes all aspects into account, doesn't rely on subjective observation by a clinician
	Sometimes, it takes too long for the patient to contact healthcare providers and the situation escalates. If CVDLINK was open for public on some level, patients could stay informed about their health
Useful potential features for a risk assessment	Easy, quick, intuitive – should not take much time to run
	Instructional, guiding system – suggests certain tests based on patient's symptoms

	Informative – to support interpretation especially with atypical symptoms
	Automated risk assessment in a busy situation when there are several patients to treat
	Combining results from longer periods of time, alerts from poor progression
Challenges or barriers	In some cases, even though an increased risk is identified, it does not affect the treatment
	In general healthcare, there are equipment to test patients, but often there's no other resources (time, staff) to do so
	Control visits to special healthcare after interventions often end after 3 months. Follow-up is in general healthcare, where specialized knowledge and resources may be unavailable
	Background info is not up to date, medication record may be outdated for years
	Patient may interact with several different specialists, who focus on their own specialty, prescribe medication etc., and other specialists don't want to question others' orders

Workshop 3

The topics discussed in this workshop were selected based on the findings in previous workshops. One group consisted of remote participants working via Teams, while the others were in-person. The topics were separated into 8 slides each containing a series of 3-5 questions. All groups managed to discuss several topics, and one group replied to all 8 slides. Topics that produced the most answers, questions, or comments were explainability, data requirements, and the idea of adding a guiding aspect to the CVDLINK platform in clinical use. In addition to the results gathered in this workshop, these topics arose in subsequent discussions during the Thessaloniki consortium meeting.

The initial summary of the workshop results is presented in Appendix 6.4. During the preliminary analysis, responses that were answered with only "yes" or "no" were excluded from the summary but were considered in the processing of the results. Efforts were made to account for repetition in the summary so that if certain questions received many similar responses, it could be assumed that participants agreed with the statements.

Some statements, such as whether data entry is done manually or whether CVDLINK can be integrated into patient information systems, revealed differing opinions between clinical and technical experts. These types of results were often related to clinical users' preferences, such as for automatic data entry, which technical experts viewed as challenging to implement. Such a statement was also selected as a topic for prioritization.

The research-oriented use of CVDLINK had received less attention in previous workshops, hence this topic was intentionally brought more into focus in this workshop. This perspective will be further expanded in a separate workshop in spring 2025.

For example, regarding the compatibility of data sources with the CVDLINK model, it was noted in the responses that WP3 includes tasks to investigate this issue, so prioritizing this question in the workshop was deemed unnecessary.

Regarding explainability, many responses were received, and consortium members understandably agreed on its importance. However, details on how to enhance explainability depend on the end-user. This is also shown in the questionnaire results and earlier workshops. The requirements for explainability differ between patient care and research work.

After the consortium meeting in Thessaloniki, task leaders arranged a session during a bi-weekly WP2 meeting via Teams. Attendees prioritised different user needs related to a topic according to their own preferences via a Teams Poll. Results are presented in Table 4, where on the left side a screenshot of Teams Poll results are shown. The prioritization is visualised with pillars; statements with lower prioritization are shown with smaller pillars. If there is not a large difference between different pillars, the statements are valued equally. On the right side, the complete statement is written open.

Table 4. Prioritization of introduced user needs by workshop participants.

Main topic	Prioritization
<p>CVDLINK SYSTEM</p> <p>The backend should be installed in the hospital (locally). Local mode...</p> <p>Entering data should be made semi-automatically so it can be verifi...</p> <p>The model should be able to deal with missing data.</p> <p>Everything should be integrated for entering data automatically to ...</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The backend should be installed in the hospital (locally). Local models are very beneficial from the point of cybersecurity. 2. Entering data should be made semi-automatically so it can be verified OK or corrected if needed. 3. The model should be able to deal with missing data. 4. Everything should be integrated for entering data automatically to CVDLINK.
<p>DATA REQUIREMENTS</p> <p>There needs to be minimum requirements for new datasets - minim...</p> <p>There should be a scientific board with clinical and technical guidan...</p> <p>There should be a focus on real world data (lifestyle factors, e.g., nu...</p> <p>The datasets used in CVDLINK must be balanced with relation to th...</p> <p>Data that isn't completely compliant with our standards, should also...</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There needs to be minimum requirements for new datasets - minimum data quality standards. 2. There should be a scientific board with clinical and technical guidance to evaluate data quality standards. 3. There should be a focus on real world data (lifestyle factors, e.g., number of steps, exposure to pollution, environment, diet/foods etc.) - these are quite important in terms of CVD risk assessment. 4. The datasets used in CVDLINK must be balanced with relation to the different countries.

	<p>5. Data that isn't completely compliant with our standards should also be included as it may also be beneficial.</p>
<p>EXPLAINABILITY</p> <p>The contribution of each parameter to the overall risk should be exp...</p> <p>CVDLINK should give information regarding how models are traine...</p> <p>The model must output calibrated uncertainty in its decisions</p> <p>Risk score should be adaptable – change in accordance to a change...</p> <p>Users should have different options for the model's output, e.g. onl...</p> <p>The risk assessment output should be placed in a context by visualis...</p> <p>The risk assessment output should include residual and absolute ris...</p> <p>Users should be trained in AI to use CVDLINK</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The contribution of each parameter to the overall risk should be explained using an "influence" score on the decision of the model. 2. CVDLINK should give information regarding how models are trained, what to expect from the models, in which cases models are applicable, accuracy, training data, etc. 3. The model must output calibrated uncertainty in its decisions 4. Risk score should be adaptable – change in accordance to a change in parameters (e.g. how the score changes if the patient quits smoking etc.) 5. Users should have different options for the model's output, e.g., only classification or classification and explanation. 6. The risk assessment output should be placed in a context by visualization 7. The risk assessment output should include residual and absolute risk per patient 8. Users should be trained in AI to use CVDLINK
<p>CVDLINK IN CLINICAL USE</p> <p>The system must provide relevant information on the tests taking in...</p> <p>CVDLINK should have an algorithm to suggest interventions/tests</p> <p>Different roles should have different levels of recommendations. A ...</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system must provide relevant information on the tests taking into account the risk/benefit of each test. Some tests have much higher risk/value. 2. CVDLINK should have an algorithm to suggest interventions/tests 3. Different roles should have different levels of recommendations. A GP may only receive recommendations to refer to a specialist. Whereas a specialist may receive recommendations to proceed to certain investigations or treatments.
<p>CVDLINK IN RESEARCH USE</p> <p>There should be a pre-filled approval form to obtain permission for ...</p> <p>There should be a different software for research use, as one could ...</p> <p>There should be a list of preapproved partners/stakeholders who ca...</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There should be a pre-filled approval form to obtain permission for data use. This could include what is usually contained in a data processing agreement. This could be

	<p>managed centrally, like a CVDLINK back office.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. There should be a different software for research use, as one could give much more detailed information to a researcher. 3. There should be a list of preapproved partners/stakeholders who can be approved more easily/faster - if you get access to one database once, you are 'preapproved' when requesting a second one (linked to a rating for an organization)
<p>AI/ML MODELS</p> <p>CVDLINK should focus on easily explainable models. An important t...</p> <p>CVDLINK should focus on deep learning algorithms for imaging dat...</p> <p>CVDLINK must use models where false negatives are very uncommon</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CVDLINK should focus on easily explainable models. An important thing here is that decision trees are much easier to interpret. When working with deep learning, we need to work on explainability so we can provide some level of explanation on why the model produces certain outputs in order to boost trust 2. CVDLINK should focus on deep learning algorithms for imaging data because they extract much more information than traditional AI multimodal models where you manually extract characteristics. 3. CVDLINK must use models where false negatives are very uncommon

Results show that, for the CVDLINK system, consortium members agree that **the backend should be installed locally in the hospital**, especially for clinical use, so that there is no need to transfer health data to the central model. This option was prioritized higher than other statements under this theme, involving suggestions on data input. As for data requirements, the **need to establish minimum requirements for new datasets** or to have a **scientific board to evaluate data quality** were ranked as higher priority than other suggestions. Considering explainability, the need for the CVDLINK tool to **offer information about its results** was seen as more important than the need for training the user in using AI in healthcare. There was not much variation in the preference scores between the options for the use of CVDLINK in clinical or research settings or on what type of AI models the system should emphasize.

3.1.3. Results from the Desk Research

Scientific articles and reports on socio-cultural differences, data sharing challenges, and overall challenges in adopting AI in healthcare are summarized in this section.

Socio-Cultural Differences

In their recent review article “Stakeholders’ perceptions of personal health data sharing: A scoping review,” Alam et al. describe global attitudes towards health data sharing, revealing that **individuals are generally motivated to share data due to its potential benefits to research, public health, and future healthcare advancements. However, privacy concerns and mistrust in data-handling entities often limit willingness to share data.** Concerns vary depending on the **type of data** (e.g., genetic vs. clinical) and the institution managing it (e.g., public vs. private organizations) (Alam, 2024). Many types of genetic data is identifying and is thus consider more critically.

Fear of re-identification and misuse of personal data are significant obstacles. It can be challenging to balance societal benefits with individual privacy and autonomy, which highlights the need for strong governance frameworks to address these concerns (Kalkman, 2022). These barriers are worsened when anonymization techniques are perceived as insufficient or when there is a history of data misuse in a given context (Alam, 2024).

There are some differences in attitudes toward data sharing between high- and low- or middle-income countries. In high-income regions (e.g., North America, Europe), attitudes are shaped by robust legal frameworks like the GDPR, which provide protections but may also complicate data sharing. In contrast, individuals in low- and middle-income countries may view data sharing more positively if it directly addresses pressing healthcare inequalities, though concerns about exploitation by wealthier countries persist (Alam, 2024). In more individualistic societies (e.g., the US), autonomy and personal consent are prioritized, while in collectivist cultures, people may be more inclined to share data for communal benefits if trust in the system is established (Kalkman, 2022).

Ethical data sharing can be ensured by respecting the process of informed consent and transparent governance. There is also a potential for power imbalances, where vulnerable populations may lack the resources or knowledge to make informed decisions about their data (Kalkman, 2022). There is a need for culturally sensitive approaches to data sharing, tailored to local trust levels, legal frameworks, and healthcare priorities (Alam, 2024).

General Challenges for AI in Healthcare

The European Commission has in 2022 published the “Study on Health Data, Digital Health and Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare” (Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (European Commission), 2022). Another EU publication, “Study on eHealth, Interoperability of Health Data and Artificial Intelligence for Health and Care in the European Union” was published in 2021 (Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (European Commission), PwC, 2021).

These studies provide a many-sided look on the issues related to implementing AI in healthcare. There are challenges in clinical, technological, ethical-regulatory, and socio-economic domains. **Clinical challenges include the need to build trust among clinicians.** Explainability is a vast concept, but with clinicians the focus can be on ensuring

safety and precision through clinical evaluations and addressing the scepticism against AI's decision-making processes.

Technological challenges include the risks of bias due to the underrepresentation of minority groups in data, lack of explainability in AI models, complicating clinical trust and application, and issues of transferability, where AI models trained in specific datasets fail to generalize.

Ethical and regulatory challenges include **absence of comprehensive frameworks** balancing innovation and accountability, regulatory uncertainties and the need for adherence to ethical principles, including transparency, equity, and responsibility.

High costs of AI implementation, including infrastructure, training, and data quality improvements are the main economic challenges. The challenge is even greater if there's an absence of appropriate financing and reimbursement models to ensure affordability.

Misunderstandings and unrealistic expectations about AI capabilities in society, resistance to data sharing and organizational adoption of AI, and a **lack of skilled healthcare professionals** trained to collaborate with AI systems are challenges on the sociocultural and organizational level.

Compatibility and Lack of EHRs

The Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra's publication addresses the challenges of health data mobility, mainly from Finland's point of view, but with insights that are transferrable to other countries in the European Union as well. A key issue with the mobility of health data in many countries is that currently, not all medical records related to an individual can be transferred electronically between healthcare units for treatment purposes. Instead, such data is often limited to the purpose of arranging care, such as referring a patient from a health centre to a hospital for specialized care (Larsio, 2023). This is the case even in Finland, although the national interface KANTA, functioning as a national data transmission and archiving service, has been functional since 2010 (Kanta s, 2024).

This issue becomes particularly prominent when a patient receives care from multiple providers. For example, this occurs when a patient moves between regions or transitions from private occupational healthcare to public specialized care. **When data is not stored in compatible formats it cannot be transferred seamlessly between systems and stays fragmented.** Existing legislation and solutions do not sufficiently address the need for system optimization and data access required for collaborative care. Transfers between systems are limited to nationally standardized data, often restricted to referral and feedback processes (Larsio, 2023).

Also, **current systems often lack summary views or search functions tailored to specific care situations.** This leads to inefficiencies as healthcare providers must manually compile relevant information from disparate sources, increasing the risk of redundant tests and procedures, suboptimal care quality with errors in health data, and missed opportunities for prevention (Larsio, 2023). A report from 2016 on the national laws on EHRs in the EU Member States describes many **differences between the contents of EHRs** in EU Member States, with some countries including much more detailed background information on patients. Common coding systems are applied in practice (such as ICD-10), but not all Member States have set legal requirements to use

common terminology or coding systems (European Commission, 2016). These differences may cause challenges in harmonizing patient background data. In a report “Health at a Glance” (OECD/EU, 2022) from 2022, 12 out of 14 reporting EU countries had requirements for minimal dataset or summary record sufficient for sharing to other health care providers. The proportion of all patients with sufficient dataset or summary record varied between 5% (Italy) and 100% (Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Luxembourg, Sweden), with the average of 77% (OECD/EU, 2022).

The optimization of the health service system to enhance care efficiency is hindered because health data moves only partially between systems. This highlights **the need for technological and procedural advancements to improve data mobility and interoperability at national and international levels**. A new shift in the health data sharing culture is anticipated by the EHDS, which aims to build an ecosystem where individuals have access to and control over their personal health data at national and EU levels. EHDS also aims to create an EU-wide market for EHR systems and provide a set-up for secondary use of health data (EC-EUR-lex, 2022).

The use of the “MyHealth@EU” infrastructure is expected to cover all Member States by 2025, and the exchange of patient summaries and electronic prescriptions will become possible (EC-EUR-lex, 2022). However, the OECD survey of EHR system development and use show that the percentage of primary care physicians using electronic medical records was 90% or lower in some countries (Italy, Czech Republic, Belgium) in 2021, and in 2016 80% or lower (Austria, France, Latvia, and Poland with only 30%) (OECD/EU, 2022), which means that **paper records still remain a concern**.

3.2 Data Interoperability and Security Requirements

Interoperability and security are key aspects of data as it can be accessed, moved, or shared between different parties. Health data is one of the most sensitive data My Health @ EU (European Commission. Directorate General for Health and Food Safety, 2020). Therefore, practitioners and researchers need to be able to share data in a common format between different entities securely. Members of the European Parliament approved the creation of the EHDS, which allows the access and transfer of electronic health records (EHR) such as patients’ electronic prescriptions, medical imagery, and laboratory results. European Health Data Space will empower the research potential of health data in an anonymised or pseudonymized format (EHDS, n.d.)). Access decisions will be made by national data access bodies. By the end of 2025, MyHealth@EU services allowing data sharing service will be established in 25 European Union countries , (MyHealth@EU, 2024). To utilize the data that came from different sources (medical units in the country or different countries), it needs to have a similar or transformable format. One source of the data could complement others, and then broader datasets might be utilized for the research with data privacy in mind. This type of interoperable and secure data usage is critical in federated learning frameworks. In fact, federated learning itself

could be one way the data from different parties might be utilized for the creation of an intelligent artificial agent (Kairouz, et al., 2021) for medical purposes. There are already a few research articles suggesting solutions or giving recommendations for challenges related to federated learning (González-García, 2021), (Cremonesi, 2023), (Cuevas-González, 2022). In the following subsections, essential data interoperability and privacy requirements are addressed.

The following sections defining the essential interoperability and data security requirements are extracted by referencing documents listed in Section 2.4.

3.2.1 Essential Data Interoperability Requirements

Interoperability is the ability for the system to read, identify, and use the information from different sources. It allows separate systems (even built using different technologies), standards, and protocols to work together. Following the requirements of interoperability is crucial for minimizing errors, streamlining data integration, and ensuring seamless information flow across different parts of the systems.

Interoperability requirements include:

- Required functionalities of the Common Data Model (CDM) such as supported data types and structures. A unified CDM ensures semantic interoperability between different parts of the federated system.
- A set of requirements for the detailed description of data structures.
- The specific metadata needs for a federated healthcare system that would allow users to identify information about the data, such as initial data provider, how the data was changed over time, and other relevant specifics of the data.
- Requirements for data aggregation from different sources (hospitals) that would allow seamless data integration. The priority is to make systems capable of identifying the structure and contents of information in a semi-automated way. Since data will be coming from different hospitals, there must be a subsystem in place to facilitate the integration of data according to the CDM.

This section contains the description of only essential interoperability requirements that include all aspects of system interoperability - common data model, metadata, data aggregation, and data discovery.

The essential interoperability requirements are:

- A CDM must be implemented on the system. This model may be based on an established or hand-crafted standard to meet specific requirements. The CDM ensures semantic interoperability across systems, enabling consistent data interpretation and exchange. During a technology requirements workshop in CVDLINK meeting at Thessaloniki, Greece, it was decided that the common data model will be based on Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) CDM.
- Detailed documentation of both data definitions and metadata specifications must be made available to the managers of the datasets as well as the end users of the system. This documentation enables users to fully understand the structure and contents of every segment of dataset.

- Before enabling the data processing of a dataset, the system must conduct integrity checks to confirm that data remains consistent and accurate. This requirement safeguards the reliability and validity of data used in analysis.
- Records of audits, including testing of safeguards, must be maintained to demonstrate the platform's compliance with security standards.
- A detailed log of all system changes, upgrades, and incidents must be kept to ensure traceability. This documentation aids in understanding system evolution and troubleshooting.
- The platform must track and document the locations of data across different versions.
- The system must maintain detailed records of the initial registration and the following versions of each dataset. This includes information on changes performed during versioning to ensure a clear and traceable history of data modifications.
- The initial registration process for datasets must include the essential administrative information, including data retention rules and other regulatory requirements. This ensures that datasets are managed in accordance with organizational and legal policies during the further processing of the data.

3.2.2 Essential Data Security Requirements

Data security addresses the requirements of a system to improve its protection against data loss, corruption and unauthorized access. These risks can arise from both external and internal threats.

Data security requirements include:

- Data security focuses on ensuring the safety, privacy, and resilience of stored data and its transmission. This aspect is crucial for safeguarding sensitive information, building user trust, and achieving compliance with data protection laws, such as, GDPR (Council of the European Union , European Parliament, 2016), EU AI Act regulations (European Commission, 2021) or national privacy laws.
- Access control and user management defines how users interact with the system, emphasizing security and accountability. Focus on preventing unauthorized access, protecting sensitive data, and ensuring operational transparency.
- Data operations and tracking, documenting, and managing data activities within the system ensure data accuracy, support legal compliance, and aid in resolving operational issues.

This section contains the description of essential data security requirements that include all aspects of data security – authentication and access, pseudonymization, data and information transfer, data storage and archiving.

The essential interoperability requirements are:

- The system must secure stored data against external and internal attacks as well as accidental disclosure.

- Measures must be implemented to prevent data loss, including robust backup strategies and recovery mechanisms.
- All data transfers must be secured to protect against unauthorized and accidental access or modifications during transit.
- Personal data, including backups and logs, must be pseudonymized to minimize the risks of breaches.
- Multi-factor authentication must be implemented to verify user identity and ensure secure access to the system.
- Comprehensive role-based access control policies must be implemented to regulate and monitor who can access specific system functionalities.
- Shared accounts are prohibited. Only personal accounts must be used to access the system to ensure accountability.
- The system must archive access requests for audit and compliance purposes.
- All data operations must be logged, including access, modifications, and deletions, to ensure traceability.
- Logs must comply with GDPR standards, including the proper handling of personal data within logs.
- The system must support versioning of data, allowing rollback or recovery of previous states in case of data deletion, rectification or updates.
- The system must maintain information related to audits and certification extensions.
- Documentation must be maintained for system changes, upgrades, and incidents, ensuring a clear history of modifications.
- Regular integrity checks must be performed on data to ensure consistency and detect unauthorized changes.
- The system must provide functionality to document and justify approval or rejection decisions, along with any associated communication in terms of data, user access and key operation changes.

3.3 Scenarios of Use

To bring user context to life, 3 different personas were developed based on the results from the process personas. The personas are connected to the CVDLINK system features, as these are described in the Description of the Action (DoA) annex of the CVDLINK grant agreement. For each persona a set of needs is defined, reflecting their expectations from the CVDLINK system. Based on these needs, different user journeys are provided describing how the system is used by each persona.

3.3.1 User Definitions

The user level is placed on top of the CVDLINK PaaS. The CVDLINK users are divided into two major groups:

a) healthcare professionals

- utilizing data-driven tools
- who are expected to apply the CVDLINK features in their everyday practice (diagnosis, prediction, and treatment),
- enhancing their objectivity and supporting their decision making,

b) target groups

- **Healthcare professionals** in need of new diagnostic and prognostic tools.
- **Research and academia** interested in developing new tools and having access to available data.
- **Technology providers** (healthcare technology solutions and service providers, innovators, payers, etc.) looking for ways to boost innovations and expand their portfolios.
- **Authorities** (EU policy makers and decision makers, national regulators and agencies, etc.) in need of more cost-effective interventions.
- **Civil society and the general public** looking to benefit from the latest innovation in the health and technology domains.

3.3.2 Personas

Persona 1: Robin 47, Cardiologist, Finland

Robin is a cardiologist from Finland who is responsible for monitoring his patients and performing assessments of cardiovascular conditions and corresponding risk, based on periodic medical examinations. The main challenges for him concern: (1) accurate risk profiling and patient stratification to optimize treatment and improve the monitoring of their conditions; (2) considering the patient characteristics, genetic predisposition, medical history; and (3) other CVD-related factors, enabling him to predict health risk and prescribe the appropriate treatment for this scope.

Table 5. Persona 1. Elicited user requirements

User Need ID	Description
CVDLINK_P1_UN_1	Accurate cardiovascular risk assessment and stratification
CVDLINK_P1_UN_2	Suggest the most appropriate treatment based on available information
CVDLINK_P1_UN_3	Accurate interpretation of results generated from different modalities

Persona 2: Nikoleta 35, Researcher, Greece

Nikoleta, 35 years old, works as a senior researcher at Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. Her main research interests include the development of AI models for the risk prediction of cardiovascular conditions. Nikoleta has collaborated with other researchers to develop an AI-driven algorithm to predict the risk of sudden cardiac arrest, utilizing past medical data as well as whole genome sequencing data available in her organization for training purposes. Despite initial positive results of her algorithm, the training data set is considered small, and thus further training is required to fully assess the performance of her work. Towards this direction, she faces challenges in finding other fully annotated, un-biased, and complete datasets, especially whole genome sequencing, as currently the existing ones remain siloed in isolated repositories that are difficult to access. In addition, legal and security concerns related to the sharing of available data further complicate access to such datasets. To this end, limited information exists on the exact contents of the dataset, making the reproduction of the algorithm's results harder.

Table 6. Persona 2. Elicited user requirements

User Need (UN) ID	Description
CVDLINK_P2_UN_1	Gain access to standardized annotated data sets
CVDLINK_P2_UN_2	Develop and train AI models
CVDLINK_P2_UN_3	Gain access to whole genome sequencing datasets
CVDLINK_P2_UN_4	Get information on the content of each training data set

Persona 3: Monica 55, CEO, Romania

Monica works as a CEO in a medical organization in Romania. Part of her duties include: (1) the expansion of the organization's portfolio through the development and testing of new AI-driven medical tools; (2) the performance of applied research, (3) the establishment of new strategic partnerships with other organizations, and (4) the optimization of the utilization of resources (infrastructure and personnel), balancing the revenues and the costs towards the value creation with new services and offerings.

Table 7. Persona 3. Elicited user requirements

User Need (UN) ID	Description
CVDLINK_P3_UN_1	Accelerate the development and training of new AI-driven tools
CVDLINK_P3_UN_2	Gain access to processing infrastructure and training resources
CVDLINK_P3_UN_3	Develop innovative solutions with reduced costs
CVDLINK_P3_UN_4	Develop strategic synergies

3.3.3 User Journeys

Robin's Journey

As a cardiologist, Robin wants to get accurate diagnostic and prognostic information for his patients and to be supported in his decision-making process related to their treatment, management, referral and risk stratification. Robin's organization has recently joined the CVDLINK system, and he decides to use the available AI-tools for his needs. After asking his organization's admin, he is registered to the system, and he receives the necessary login credentials to join the platform and get access to the available AI tools and services.

After uploading patient data, Robin proceeds with using the AI tools of the CVDLINK platform. He is interested in the tools related to the risk of sudden cardiac arrest that combine historical, physiological, and genetic data, as well as tools related to feature extraction of cardiac sounds and other signals which will enable him to take informed decisions on patient treatment. After the completion of the data process, he is able to review the results visually, trace back to the data used for their production, as well as utilize the CVDLINK annotation functionality to include further information on the results produced, enriching the final outcomes. All the above will facilitate his coordinating role in patient management, enabling him to organize his referrals better and more accurately.

All results are combined with a confidence indicator. Upon completion of the process, he can provide positive or negative feedback on the results produced, contributing in this way to the further improvement of the tools.

Nikoleta's Journey

A fellow researcher of Nikoleta recommended CVDLINK and presented her with the advantages provided by the platform, related to access to training datasets that can be used for the development of AI models. In order to access the features of the platforms, she proceeds with creating a researcher account. Upon completing the necessary verification and activation procedures, she gains access to the system. After accepting the terms of use, she is in a position to start using the research features provided by the platform. To this end, a short on-boarding process takes place, where Nikoleta is introduced to the main features and functionalities of CVDLINK.

One of her first actions in the system is to search for available datasets that can be used for training her AI algorithm. After inserting the corresponding criteria, she can retrieve a catalogue of the most relevant datasets available in the platform, along with details related to their contents, metadata, openness, and ownership status.

She first confirms that the CVDLINK datasets can support the training needs of her algorithms and that they are available for this scope. As CVDLINK doesn't permit any direct access to data or the downloading of any dataset, Nikoleta needs to utilize the CVDLINK framework functions in order to be able to train her algorithm. Thus, she defines the type and other relevant parameters of the model to be trained on the platform, using

the visualization features available for this scope. After the completion of the necessary quality checks the definition process is completed. She then proceeds with the selection of the datasets of her interest to be used in the training process. Nikoleta does not need to worry about ethical and privacy concerns, as the datasets used are de-identified and adequate permissions are already in place. In addition, the CVDLINK common data model ensures a harmonized data format, facilitating the training process.

By utilizing the visual tools provided by CVDLINK she is now able to monitor the training progress as well as generate reports and download the results of this process. Last but not least, CVDLINK provides Nikoleta with the ability to publish her algorithm, facilitating her to share her work with other researchers who are members of the CVDLINK platform. To this end, the platform enables her to define the level of openness as well as sharing terms.

Monica's Journey

Having received promising results regarding a new AI-driven model for the prediction of cardiac risk, Monica understands the commercialization potential of this new feature. Currently the model is trained with only a few datasets available to her organization, and gaining access to the resources needed for the tool to reach commercial maturity (in terms of performance) poses an additional challenge to be tackled. In order to address these problems, she decides that her organization should join the CVDLINK platform.

To this end, a corresponding subscription needs to take place, enabling her organization to join the CVDLINK ecosystem. Based on this, her organization will have access to other training datasets, which will enable further training of the AI-driven tool. Furthermore, the organization will gain access to other processing resources provided by the CVDLINK platform, facilitating the acceleration of the training procedure, without the need to maintain such an infrastructure on premise or employ specialized personnel.

In addition, in order to support the research and development activities, she decides that her organization should join the CVDLINK federated repository (setting a federated node on premise) as a data provider, sharing a subset of the internally available datasets (legally suitable for this scope). From her point of view, such activities constitute a collaboration arm that facilitates the establishment of synergies with other data providers on a win-win basis. Towards this end, the CVDLINK platform already provides the necessary tools for data quality control, de-identification and harmonization, as well as incorporates the necessary framework for defining sharing rules and controlling data access rules and openness, supporting the sharing practices and scope.

3.4 Initial Definition of Business Processes

3.4.1 Business Processes

The business processes (BP) are envisioned here as a more abstract, first level of system requirements. **Four** main sources of business processes are considered in our case: (1) the Grant Agreement (CVDLINK Consortium, 2023), where the concept and the main

requirements of CVDLINK are defined; (2) user input and the user requirements definition process, based on the analysis and work performed in the context of CVDLINK Work Package 2; (3) this current deliverable (D2.1); and (4) the work already taking place in the context of the rest of the technical WPs (WP3-5), where partners are collaboratively analysing the specific requirements of each WP.

Table 8. Mapping the business process with the project tasks

ID	Title	Description	Reference (or derived from)
CVDLINK-BP-01	The user shall be able to get system responses in a timely fashion	All system functions including maintenance and upgrading should be transparent and robust to the users.	Quality of Service Best Practices
CVDLINK-BP-02	The user shall have the necessary resources to run the models	The execution times of running or training a model should be acceptable, thus the necessary processing resources should be available for this scope.	CVDLINK_P2_UN_2, CVDLINK_P3_UN_2, DoA (T6.1)
CVDLINK-BP-03	The user must be able to understand what kind of data is available in the system	Information on the datasets stored in the CVDLINK federated storage shall be able to be retrieved by performing corresponding queries.	DoA (T3.2), CVDLINK_P2_UN_4
CVDLINK-BP-04	The user shall store the data locally	Datasets shall be stored in the place of the production and the access provided only through the federated platform	DoA (T3.6)

CVDLINK-BP-05	The user should be able to train AI models using federated approaches	During the training process, the CVDLINK platform should be able to aggregate the model's training results to produce a more complete one.	DoA (T4.6), CVDLINK_P2_UN_2
CVDLINK-BP-06	The user needs to perform all functions respecting all legal and ethical aspects	The system should make sure that all aspects related to data management (processing and storage) are addressed based on established legal and ethical norms.	DoA (T5.1, T5.2, T5.4), CVDLINK_P2_UN_1, CVDLINK_P3_UN_2
CVDLINK-BP-07	The user needs to perform all functions in a secure manner	The system shall guarantee secure performance of operations, data management, as well as transactions' transparency.	DoA (T3.4, T4.6)
CVDLINK-BP-08	The user needs to utilize harmonized datasets	The datasets shall be harmonized following a common data model (CDM) provided by CVDLINK.	DoA (T3.3), CVDLINK_P2_UN_1, CVDLINK_P2_UN_3, CVDLINK_P3_UN_2
CVDLINK-BP-09	The user shall be able to link the results with the datasets used for their generation	The system shall make available specific functionalities to enable data traceability to ensure credibility of the results.	DoA (T4.6), CVDLINK_P1_UN_3, CVDLINK_P2_UN_2

CVDLINK-BP-10	The user shall use de-identified datasets for feeding the AI-models	Data used in federated fashion is inherently “de-identified”.	DoA (T3.3, T3.6, T3.8), CVDLINK_P2_UN_1, CVDLINK_P2_UN_3, CVDLINK_P3_UN_2
CVDLINK-BP-11	The user shall be able to annotate results and datasets	The system shall provide the necessary mechanism enabling the (semi-automated) annotation of the datasets and results.	DoA (T3.5), CVDLINK_P2_UN_1
CVDLINK-BP-12	The users shall perform quality checks before uploading a dataset on the CVDLINK federated repository	System shall be able to identify whether data that will be uploaded follow a predefined set of requirements defined in CVDLINK (e.g., follow the same de-identification protocol, include all the mandatory fields, and encodings, etc.).	DoA (T3.3)
CVDLINK-BP-13	The user shall be able to get the results in a visual manner	The users shall be able to perform action and consume CVDLINK services visually as well as get results visualizations.	DoA (T4.4, T4.8), CVDLINK_P1_UN_1, CVDLINK_P1_UN_2, CVDLINK_P2_UN_2, CVDLINK_P3_UN_1
CVDLINK-BP-14	The user shall receive information per searched dataset	Each dataset in the federated repository shall include a detailed description that will facilitate users increasing their	DoA (T3.2, T3.6, T3.8), CVDLINK_P2_UN_4, CVDLINK_P3_UN_2

		discoverability, quality control and utilization.	
CVDLINK-BP-15	The AI models should be self-explainable	The CVDLINK platform should incorporate methods for AI explainability, to tackle the "black-box" effect of AI algorithms.	DoA (T4.6), CVDLINK_P1_UN_3, CVDLINK_P2_UN_2
CVDLINK-BP-16	The user should use the results of AI models for decision support	The trained AI models should be made available to users for informed decision making on various CVD conditions.	DoA (T4.1, T4.2, T4.3 T4.8), CVDLINK_P1_UN_2
CVDLINK-BP-17	The user should get support for patient stratification	The system should integrate data from different data sources and calculate features related to patients' conditions, leading to better stratification and guiding clinical action.	DoA (T4.8), CVDLINK_P1_UN_1
CVDLINK-BP-18	The user should receive information on patient risk for different CVD conditions	The system shall provide (predictive) information on patient risk based on CVD conditions assessment.	DoA (T4.8), CVDLINK_P1_UN_1
CVDLINK-BP-19	The user shall receive notifications that the AI training and inference processes are completed	The system shall perform training and inference processes asynchronously, notifying the users	DoA (T4.7, T4.8), CVDLINK_P2_UN_2

		when such jobs are completed.	
CVDLINK-BP-20	The user shall utilize CVDLINK features based on his/her role	The system shall enable the use of its features based on the users' role, assigned to them when joining the system.	DoA (T3.2, T5.1)
CVDLINK-BP-21	The user shall agree on terms of use before using the CVDLINK platform	Before using any feature of the CVDLINK system the users shall be notified of the terms and agree with them.	DoA (T5.1, T5.2, T5.4)
CVDLINK-BP-22	The user shall be able to share information on searched datasets with other members of the CVDLINK platform	The system shall enable sharing of search queries and federated training datasets, enabling the user to set the rules of the sharing process.	DoA (T3.2, T3.6, T3.8), CVDLINK_P2_UN_2, CVDLINK_P3_UN_4
CVDLINK-BP-23	The user should be able to share an AI model with other members of the CVDLINK platform	The system shall allow the user to share AI models, enabling the user to set the rules of the sharing process.	DoA (T4.4, T4.8), CVDLINK_P2_UN_2, CVDLINK_P3_UN_4
CVDLINK-BP-24	The user should be able to make use of the interoperability features of CVDLINK with external EU infrastructures	The platform should provide integration with external EU infrastructures, for publishing tools and datasets as well as utilizing their resources.	DoA (T3.7), CVDLINK_P3_UN_2, CVDLINK_P3_UN_3

3.4.2 Role Specifications

This section defines the CVDLINK system roles. The roles define the access rights and the actions that can be performed by the users (assigned with this role). Six main system roles are foreseen:

- 1) **The CVDLINK User:** a high-level role that maintains common access rights and actions that users will be able to perform.
- 2) **The CVDLINK Healthcare Professional:** involving all access rights and actions for using the system in medical practice.
- 3) **The CVDLINK Researcher:** involving access rights and features for utilizing the system for research purposes.
- 4) **The CVDLINK Resource Manager:** a systemic role for handling the system resources.
- 5) **The CVDLINK Super Admin:** involving all features to manage users (organizations and single users) of the CVDLINK platform and ensure security and GDPR compliance.
- 6) **The CVDLINK Organization Admin:** involving all features to handle the role management and access of organization users as well as organization related aspects.

Table 9. CVDLINK Role. User

The CVDLINK User	
Role ID	CVDLINK_RO_1
Description	The user is a basic role, including all common (basic) functionalities that all other CVDLINK system roles may perform. Thus, at the time a new user is created, firstly it is assigned the role "User" followed by other required roles.
Related Business Processes	CVDLINK-BP-03, CVDLINK-BP-04, CVDLINK-BP-06, CVDLINK-BP-07, CVDLINK-BP-09, CVDLINK-BP-11, CVDLINK-BP-13, CVDLINK-BP-15, CVDLINK-BP-21

Table 10. CVDLINK Role. Healthcare Professional

The CVDLINK Healthcare Professional	
Role ID	CVDLINK_RO_2
Description	This role uses the platform as a tool in the current medical practice by utilizing CVDLINK services related to the risk management and stratification of CVD

	conditions. The main scope of these services is to support healthcare professionals in making informed decisions, optimizing care and treatment.
Related Business Processes	CVDLINK-BP-16, CVDLINK-BP-17, CVDLINK-BP-18

Table 11, CVDLINK Role. Researcher

The CVDLINK Researcher	
Role ID	CVDLINK_RO_3
Description	This role uses the system for testing research hypotheses as well as for the development and training of AI models, by accessing available datasets and CVDLINK processing resources. This role will have the ability to share the results of his/her work with other members of CVDLINK (belonging to the same organization or external ones).
Related Business Processes	CVDLINK-BP-05, CVDLINK-BP-08, CVDLINK-BP-10, CVDLINK-BP-12, CVDLINK-BP-14, CVDLINK-BP-19, CVDLINK-BP-22, CVDLINK-BP-23, CVDLINK-BP-24

Table 12. CVDLINK Role. Resource Manager

The CVDLINK Resource Manager	
Role ID	CVDLINK_RO_4
Description	The resource manager is a systemic automation in charge of providing configurations or actions over the system in order to configure it, ensuring the availability of processing resources, timely responses of the CVDLINK platform and overall QoS and SLA.
Related Business Processes	CVDLINK-BP-01, CVDLINK-BP-02

Table 13. CVDLINK Role. Super Admin

The CVDLINK Super Admin	
Role ID	CVDLINK_RO_5
Description	This role handles all administrative aspects of the role, data and AI model management from the CVDLINK

	platform's side, ensuring privacy and security preservation and GDPR compliance. This role does not have any rights/access to medical data processing/management services as well as to the consumption of the CVDLINK AI features.
Related Business Processes	CVDLINK-BP-20

Table 14. CVDLINK Role. Organization Admin

The CVDLINK Organization Admin	
Role ID	CVDLINK_RO_6
Description	This role is responsible for managing administrative aspects for organizations participating in the CVDLINK ecosystem. The main operations of this role are the role and access management of the organization members to the CVDLINK platform, as well as performing activities related to administrative aspects of the organization's data sets and data sharing procedures. This role does not have any rights or access to medical data processing and management services, or to use the CVDLINK AI features.
Related Business Processes	CVDLINK-BP-20, CVDLINK-BP-22, CVDLINK-BP-23

4 Conclusions

According to the results reported in this deliverable, the need to identify high risk patients in general healthcare remains a challenge for which AI-based tools may provide a solution. The general opinion according to the results obtained through the international questionnaire and workshops is that the risk assessment models should be trained with diverse data obtained from several locations. Challenges in accessing health datasets have slowed development in this domain but federated approaches have the potential to overcome these challenges. However, several hurdles remain. There are different opinions on the sharing of health data for secondary use, but justification can be sought by considering ethical and regulatory policies while respecting individuals' rights and concerns.

As for the implementation of AI in healthcare, the clinicians' point of view often emphasizes the evidence-based approach. Explainability in AI does not only support decision-making but promotes the development of clinicians' trust in AI. **Explainability** can be enhanced in several ways, but the transparency in the uncertainty of the results is a highly valuable feature especially in patient care. There may be unrealistic expectations with respect to the efficiency of AI-based tools in healthcare and therefore it is needed to be very informative regarding the shortcomings and uncertainties. Implementation also requires financial, educational, and long-term investments from the organization. This can mean change management, user support, and evaluation of ensuring the realization of the targeted benefits. A positive finding was that a large majority of the questionnaire recipients were open to the clinical use of AI.

The investigations conducted so far **did not uncover major differences in social and cultural perspectives** with regards to data sharing or attitudes towards AI, aside from the fact that respondents in high-income countries are generally more strict about data sharing, likely due to a longer history of regulations. Another key finding is that **sharing genetic data is viewed more critically** than sharing clinical data.

Identified major **pain-points** regarding training new AI-based models and using them for making risk assessments are related to **data availability**. There are not many comprehensive datasets available that would include several data modalities, i.e., genetic data, signal data such as ECG, imaging data such as coronary angiography, and clinical background data containing reliable endpoint information, which limits the possibilities to train new efficient AI models. When data is available, it should be **harmonized** for universal use. Challenge related to this is that unified coding systems are not always used. Datasets formed through the secondary use of data originally collected for healthcare purposes have the limitation of **missing data** because only the tests required for patient treatment have been made. Further, genetics data is seldom collected for clinical treatment purposes. The question and challenge to be investigated and solved is how much missing information can be tolerated and imputed without significantly affecting the performance of the developed models.

Vast variation in utilized data formats and **low usage of data standards** is an issue currently slowing the integration of multimodal analytics tools in clinical practice. It can be anticipated that in the future the significance of this obstacle will diminish as the use

of data standards increases. In research use, the findings on collecting, transferring, and re-using health data can help with designing federated platforms for other specialities as well. The results gathered in this deliverable and presented in the form of business processes in Section 3.4 will provide a basis for the CVDLINK design, with the needs of different users considered.

The work on refining the identified user requirements and business processes will continue and these will be formulated as technical requirements that will be reported by M18 in CVDLINK deliverable D2.2.

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6 Appendices

This section includes verbatim results of the applied questionnaire and run workshops.

6.1 Description of the distribution of the on-line questionnaire

In Israel, the questionnaire was distributed to the heads of cardiology departments across the country, as well as to contact persons of key healthcare providers in the community. They, in turn, were asked to share the questionnaire link with the physicians and nurses in their departments. Additionally, the Israeli Health Organization and the Israeli Cardiology Organization included the link in their weekly newsletters. HYMC also promoted the questionnaire by posting the link on various media platforms, the HYMC Facebook and LinkedIn profiles, and the Israeli Cardiology Organization LinkedIn Page.

In Finland, the questionnaire was forwarded to several health care centres via contacts working in The Wellbeing Services County of Pirkanmaa (PirHA). In PirHA, as well as in other Wellbeing Services Counties, it is obligatory to apply for a permit to conduct a study aimed at workers in the area, even when replies are anonymous. A separate application process was finalized on August 16th. The questionnaire was distributed to multiple health centres in PirHA and to different wards in Tampere Heart Hospital. A separate questionnaire form was used in the Tampere Heart Hospital that included the same questions as the EU Survey platform. Additionally, this form included the opportunity to leave contact information in case the recipient volunteered to take part in a separate workshop (Workshop 2 of Task 2.3).

In Greece, the questionnaire was distributed in English. A list of potential stakeholders, particularly clinicians, was prepared. To maximize participation and visibility, the questionnaire was distributed directly to stakeholders and shared on the AUTH's School of Medicine's social media platforms.

Ethical approval was not required in Greece, as informed consent was incorporated within the survey, and best practices were followed for anonymous data collection.

In Estonia, the Clinical Research Centre was contacted for advice regarding the distribution of medical questionnaires among Estonian doctors. Based on the Centre's advice, partners sent the questionnaire to the Estonian Society of Cardiology, which forwarded it to their society members. The questionnaire that had been prepared by CVDLINK partners on the EU Survey platform was distributed in English. No ethics approval was required because the questionnaire, as well as the accompanying letter, included informed consent and the questionnaire was anonymous.

Other distribution channels were also utilized. Antti Vehkaoja (TAU) presented the CVDLINK project during the PARQ Cost Action meeting in Vienna in May 2024. As part of the presentation, he shared a QR code which allowed interested people to sign up to answer the questionnaire. Those people who signed up were sent the link to answer after the questionnaire on August 6th.

Trilateral also distributed the questionnaire on CVDLINK's social media platforms, potentially reaching clinical experts outside specific medical centres as well. The questionnaire was advertised multiple times on CVDLINK's LinkedIn page, directly reaching the 200+ page followers and many more people through likes and reposts, and shared on the project website and newsletter.

6.2 Questions relevant to CVDLINK identified by the workshop 1 participants.

HOW	<p>1 How this compares with current risk scores, what to do if other says high risk and other says low risk?</p> <p>2 How will CVDLINK facilitate gender equality?</p> <p>3 How do we keep this tool relevant across time?</p> <p>4 How is data bias assessed?</p> <p>5 How it would be adapted to other specialities?</p> <p>6 How will it be used in the general population?</p> <p>7 How will it be implemented at the EU level?</p> <p>8 How and when will the tool be updated?</p> <p>9 How can I publish the results?</p> <p>10 How reliable is this tool?</p> <p>11 Will it be deployed locally or globally, how many instances?</p> <p>12 How will it change the daily work of cardiologist?</p> <p>13 How will it be accessed?</p>
WHEN	<p>14 When (in which stage) of pathology should we use this tool?</p> <p>15 When is it ethical to use this tool?</p> <p>16 When do you choose to apply this tool?</p> <p>17 When will the development of this tool stop? Is it continuous?</p> <p>18 Could it be used in primary, secondary or tertiary prevention?</p> <p>19 When will AI decisions be explained to end users?</p>
WHAT	<p>20 Are there any risks associated with the tool and how do we mitigate them?</p> <p>21 What happens if there is a data breach?</p>

	<p>22 What medical parameters can I get from this tool?</p> <p>23 What is the added value of the tool?</p> <p>24 What impact will it have on patients?</p> <p>25 What's the cost or terms of use?</p> <p>26 What is the pricing model of the tool?</p> <p>27 What is the non-clinical benefit of the tool?</p> <p>28 What is the expected benefit to the CVDLINK partners?</p> <p>29 What are the major drawbacks of this kind of system?</p> <p>30 Which coronary artery is more important to MACE?</p> <p>31 What is the main goal of the tool?</p>
WHO	<p>32 Who would pay for using the tool, who is the customer?</p> <p>33 Who will decide if new data is included?</p> <p>34 Who is going to use it?</p> <p>35 Who will be the system manager – locally and overall?</p> <p>36 Who will be able to access the tool, only clinicians or also patients?</p> <p>37 Who should be trained to train others to use the tool?</p> <p>38 Which medical specialities are in the highest need for this kind of tool?</p>
WHY	<p>39 Why should someone pay for use?</p> <p>40 Why would I trust this tool?</p> <p>41 Why to use this tool in comparison to others in the market?</p>
WHERE	<p>42 Where will this tool be in storage?</p> <p>43 Will it be used in outpatient or inpatient practice or both?</p> <p>44 Will it be used in primary care or special care?</p> <p>45 Where does the tool work? Universal?</p>

6.3 Points raised in the follow-up discussion with all workshop 1 participants.

Discussed benefits:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The tool will strengthen overall prediction by taking all the different parameters into account; results are therefore more specific. -The change will be visible for patients, not for cardiologists. Maybe the cardiologist will have to work even more. -It is a decision-making tool – confident tools are needed! -It is more tailor-made than other tools -It is not meant to replace other risk assessments, but to modify and add information; flag patients with high risk -On one point the tool could be more important to primary caretaker or patients than cardiologists; can be used to flag those patients who never see cardiologists until heart attack
Discussed issues:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -You can detect high risk patient sometimes even with your own eyes – giving an estimate with the tool doesn't do much of a change. However, there's a need to quantify the risk -AI can give you an answer, will you make decisions based on it? -If you have different scores with traditional tools and CVDLINK, what do you do? What is the added benefit in these cases? Do you go by heart? -One opinion was that you can't use it for everyone – at least some level of cardiological expertise must be sought when using the tool -If you release the tool for everyone, people might start using it for other reasons too. It can cause harm when used incorrectly -Needs trial to validate -Needs another vertical to the tool that will upload results to patient management systems
Raised questions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Could this tool identify high risk patients that could benefit from intervention from those who don't? -For some patients it is obvious that they are in high risk - can the tool spot those who are not obviously high-risk patients? -Can it detect high risk for something severe (CVD-related), when there's no risk for anything else? -Could it be used to identify patients who we can provide even expensive treatment to, that can benefit from it – aim expenses for the targeted group of patients -What will the outcomes of CVDLINK clinical studies be? This will aid us for right direction

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -There were different opinions about whether the general population should be able to use the tool; could it be used by policy makers, gatekeepers, nurses, primary health care -Primary caretaker is a gatekeeping system. If a GP could use CVDLINK, it could avoid misuse of specialists -How about preventive use? Can you monitor patients through time?
<p style="text-align: center;">New ideas</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -What can a patient or a nurse do? Nurse can flag patients and consult doctors -How many people come to the ER, are given paracetamol, develop heart attack because of lack of intervention; these patients could be spotted with CVDLINK tool -The tool could give advice to see neurologist instead of cardiologist -There could be different layers to the tool: First layer is to prevent: gatekeeper; GPs or nurses could use this tool for patients that raise concern Second layer: cardiologist; with their expertise, they could use the tool with more precise actions – should it be modified for cardiologists? Also, for monitoring the progression Third layer: patients can use the application themselves. Access to personal health data is already here with wearable technology, lab results in own phone; patients could use a simplified version of the tool -It should give integrated reference to the data that is given to the general population (e.g., your risk is 40% when in general it is 15%); results need to be reported in a different way with GPs, cardiologists, public etc, also for pharma or research -Promising many things means practically nothing. There’s a need to prioritize, some things might be exclusive for different users

6.4 Discussion topics of workshop 3

1. CVDLINK SW – PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION

- Although training of the CVDLINK models is done in the federated platform being developed, the models could later be used by a separate software without this platform.
- Especially for the clinical use, is there a need for a locally deployed separate software for running the CVDLINK prediction models only, especially from the cybersecurity and practical approvals point of view?
- Is there some benefits for having everything in just one software?
- Would there be any benefits from a separate SW in the research use?

2. REQUIREMENTS FOR INPUT DATA

- There can be differences between countries on which data they routinely collect in clinical practice and which tests are done on regular basis.
- How/who should check the new data sources for compatibility with CVDLINK before addition?
- Should we define minimum requirements for new datasets?
- Do you come up with other requirements for data sources?
- How can data be harmonized in case there are different criteria in different countries e.g. for declaring SCD?

3. REQUIREMENTS ON EXPLAINABILITY

- Explainability has been recognized as an important aspect in medical AI.
- How should AI decisions be explained to end users?
- Should the contribution of each parameter to the overall risk be explained?
- How should the output value of the tool, e.g. risk-% of SCA/SCD be placed in a context?
- How should the results be presented so that they support decision-making?

4. USAGE OF CVDLINK IN CLINICAL PRACTICE

- Patient background data can be scattered in several EHR's. There can be differences between countries, and sometimes information needs to be collected from several sources to build a complete patient status.
- Can it be tolerated that all the data is entered manually or should the CVDLINK system include integrations to patient health records?
- Is it possible in practice that some new data (that otherwise would not be collected) is collected only for the purpose of using the CVDLINK tool?

5. RELEVANT DATA THAT IS CURRENTLY NOT BEING COLLECTED

- Several such data types relevant to CVD's have been identified to exist, that are not currently being collected in clinical practice. These include, e.g. nourishment and patient activity information.
- Do you think that this information should be collected? Is it feasible/possible in practice?

- What kind of collection methods would be preferred?
- Should CVDLINK have an integration to data platforms of wellness device manufacturers?

6. CVDLINK AS A GUIDING, ASSISTIVE SYSTEM

- Especially in general practice, symptoms may go unnoticed or be misunderstood, and certain tests are not conducted because of a lack of specialized knowledge.
- Could there be an advisory program in CVDLINK regarding decision making in health care; not only giving results but also suggesting interventions or more tests?
- Could CVDLINK make a risk-benefit assessment that would help aim expensive treatment to patients who are more likely to benefit from them?
- Different users may be equipped differently when it comes to inserting data to CVDLINK or interpreting the results. Should there be different modes to choose from based on the user? For example, GP vs. cardiologist

7. USE OF CVDLINK TOOL IN RESEARCH

- It has been recognized that using health data also in federated way requires case-specific approval. E.g. utilizing certain biobank data for training a model for new purpose requires new approval.
- To your knowledge, is this always the case (except for publicly available datasets)?
- How could the approval process be made easier?
- Could there be joint/automated approval process facilitated by CVDLINK or does the user need to apply separately for each dataset?

8. SUPPORTED AI/ML MODEL TYPES

- There is huge variation of different types of AI models that can be trained such as decision trees, neural networks...
- What types of models should the CVDLINK be able to create?
- Is there a need for deep learning algorithms?

6.5 Initial summary of results from workshop 3

1. CVDLINK SOFTWARE – PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION 1

Especially for clinical use, is there a need for locally deployed separate software for running the CVDLINK prediction models only?

- Yes, the backend should be installed in the hospital (locally)
- Depends on the model (when genetic data is involved – local; if it only includes general data (like clinical score measurements) – website would work too)
- Training the model and using it are separate processes, so it shouldn't be a problem to put it in a local software.
- With centralized deployment, if you want to engage with data, you need to send your data somewhere.

Are there some benefits to having everything in just one software?

- Easier to use once you got familiar with the software + User registration + uniform treatment of data
- Data security and ethical considerations, ease of system use. Allow rare disease analysis.
- Are we talking about having all of the models in the same software – probably yes, in the sense that if we want to make a decision based on different data types we should have a centralized space where clinicians can see all the information together.
- When you are working in federated systems – if the data doesn't leave the owner, the owner needs to have some sort of local software. There are a few elements for data privacy that can't leave/be uploaded somewhere
- One big software might however also be susceptible to outages, whereas multiple smaller independent software don't have this problem.
- Local models are very beneficial from the point of cybersecurity. Have an online and offline version of the software.

Would there be any benefits from a separate SW in the research use?

- Privacy! Enable inference without sharing data. Scalability.
- When writing software, you're probably working mostly on your own computer. There would be research benefits to be able to create on your own software and then share with others – that would enable experimentation
- A different version for research use would definitely be beneficial, as one could give much more detailed information to a researcher

2. REQUIREMENTS FOR INPUT DATA

How/who should check the new data sources for compatibility with CVDLINK before addition?

- WP3 includes a specific task related to this – Task leader SIMAVI is responsible

- Vicom has previously implemented a digital patient model outlining characteristics people need to make data adhere to

Should we define minimum requirements for new datasets?

- CVDLINK internal definition of requirements/principles (predefined)
- We must have minimal requirements for datasets/data -> Mandatory fields. The minimal requirements must be considered during the prospective studies.
- The laboratory tests for prospective studies must be standardized across countries.
- Patient number, minimum data (medical history, socio-demographics)
- Ethical compliance. Anonymized data. Data structure and quality.

How can data be harmonized in case there are different criteria in different countries e.g. for declaring SCD?

- Could try to implement standard OMOP terminologies
- Perhaps we need to learn about the particularities of each country in order to better understand the data we have. E.g., there may be legal aspects for declaring SCD unique to each country.

3. REQUIREMENTS ON EXPLAINABILITY

How should AI decisions be explained to end users?

- Highlight top 3 of most important factors in determining a risk
- Target group-oriented explanation (interface of the dashboard for clinicians which makes it explainable for the doctors to their patients (including more complex data as well as visualizations for the explanation to the patients))
- Recommendation on final decision. Visualization. Feature importance. Justification of the output. Performance accuracy/strength of recommendation. How the model was trained and in which data. Interaction between AI output and clinician
- We may need to add more explanations/context for non-experienced users.
- The model must also output calibrated uncertainty in its decisions.
- Physicians would like to know the research behind the model at a superficial level. And it is important to know that the model has been trained on a big, unbiased dataset and is therefore reliable.
- The contribution of the most important parameters to the overall risk should be explained

How should the output value of the tool, e.g. risk-% of SCA/SCD be placed in a context?

- Text-based, graphs for visualization
- Visualization of risk instead of % (range of risk groups), Interactive results (clinician asks for specific metrics)
- Residual and stratified absolute risk per patient

How should the results be presented so that they support decision-making?

- Text-based, graphs for visualization, Visualization of prediction
- Risk score should be adaptable – change in accordance to a change in parameters (e.g. how the score changes if the patient quits smoking etc.)

- Treatment recommendation and potential outlook of disease progression would be useful

How should AI decisions be explained to end users?

- At least, we should give minimum information regarding how models are trained, what to expect from the models, in which cases models are applicable, accuracy, training data, etc. These factors should all be explained. We should try to provide information on why a model produces a certain output. For example, if I want to classify an image as healthy or unhealthy, you want to point to specific elements in the image that support the conclusion that the image shows an unhealthy heart, etc.
- From a clinician's POV, it's helpful to understand the training data. E.g., the clinician can say this was trained on 1,000 scans, the accuracy rates, etc.
- Medical students need to be trained in AI, so they have training to help them discern whether an AI tool is accurately trained.

Has the contribution of each parameter to the overall risk been explained?

- this would be very good from clinicians' POV. Technical partners agree this is achievable and important

How should the output value of the tool, e.g. risk-% of SCA/SCD be placed in a context?

- It's not just about developing models and providing the outputs. We have a task for user services focused on presenting this information. We should have a clinical decision support system where you can show the data and the output of the models. Ideally this would integrate patient data from different sources to support decision-making and run the models on top of that.
- Now, we have the risk score in cardiology. Considering age, gender, exposure to smoking, blood pressure, cholesterol, we are able to estimate the 10-year risk of having a cardiovascular event or stroke. With this tool, by integrating all this big data, we will be able to produce more refined risk assessments. From a clinicians' POV it would be a refined version of this risk assessment

How should the results be presented so that they support decision-making?

- Clinician POV: same as above, related to previous efforts to promote new mode of communicating to patients - 'life expectancy benefits'. Presenting risk assessment in terms of shared decision-making by showing them that if they stop smoking, start exercising, they might have a life expectancy benefit of 20 years. Studies found that this more positive way of communicating had more positive results than saying you'll die in 10 years.

4. USAGE OF CVDLINK IN CLINICAL PRACTICE

Can it be tolerated that all the data is entered manually or should the CVDLINK system include integrations to patient health records?

- Manual: human errors possible
- e.g. OMOP integration would be good
- From a clinical POV, it'd be great to have everything integrated. Tech partners say no. All the legal and ethical hurdles would be too much

- CVDLINK should be prepared for interconnection and if the patient decides they want to share data with CVDLINK the data should go there. It's the patient's decision, not the operators.
- Need someone to verify everything is OK or do corrections if needed. Not all countries have EHR though. Does the country have central registry that could be utilized in this kind of integration?

Is it possible in practice that some new data (that otherwise would not be collected) is collected only for the purpose of using CVDLINK tool?

- Not in clinical practice now
- The model should be able to deal with missing data.

5. RELEVANT DATA CURRENTLY NOT BEING COLLECTED

Several such data types relevant to CVD's have been identified to exist, that are not currently being collected in clinical practice. These include, e.g. nourishment and patient activity information. Do you think this information should be collected? Is it feasible/possible in practice?

- Depends on agreement of the patient
- Images from scans are analyzed but not saved – these could be useful for AI training
- At the moment, focus on real world data (lifestyle factors, e.g., number of steps, exposure to pollution, environment, diet/foods etc.) - these are quite important in terms of CVD risk assessment.
- If collected, e.g. patient activity information is likely sparse and techs (watches) are divers

What kind of collection methods would be preferred?

- questionnaire, interviews
- Automatic integrations ideal, in e.g. activity watches would work. Standardized questionnaires, high-throughput blood panels (NMR). Microbiome in the gut.

Should CVDLINK have an integration to data platforms of wellness device manufacturers?

- Why not, after considering ethical and legal aspects, terms of use, data access committees, etc.
- Would be useful to collect basic information, e.g., steps per day, burned calories, and other factors related to lifestyle. Current wearables are not medically certified and therefore couldn't be used in a medical algorithm. But collecting lifestyle data could be useful and easy to collect via patient's phone
- this needs to be one standard device.

6. CVDLINK AS A GUIDING, ASSISTIVE SYSTEM

Could there be an advisory program in CVDLINK regarding decision making in health care; not only giving results but also suggesting interventions or more tests?

- To support CDS, counseling in terms of training/ simulation

- It could be valuable for front line family doctors, emergency doctors that are not specialized cardiologists
- Different roles could have different levels of recommendations. A GP may only receive recommendations to refer to a specialist. Whereas a specialist may receive recommendations to proceed to certain investigations or treatments. E.g. angioplasty

Could CVDLINK make a risk-benefit assessment that would help aim expensive treatment to patients who are more likely to benefit from them?

- Clinicians should be provided with information on level of risk (High risk patients and low risk patients) which could guide the diagnostic algorithm (what kind of imaging would be performed) E.g. echo cardiography, angio CT/coronography/angiography that all have different costs and risk benefit for patients. With better patient stratification treatment costs and health outcomes.
- No! (discrimination issues)
- Should be the doctor's decision to make a cost efficiency evaluation. Ethical issues surrounding communicating cost-efficiency information to patients in relation to life expectancy (e.g. your life expectancy doesn't justify the cost of intervention) Different users may be equipped differently when it comes to inserting data to CVDLINK or interpreting the results.

Should there be different modes to choose from based on the user? For example, GP vs. Cardiologist

- No (equally qualified, trained and technically equipped etc.)
- Another end user could be researchers trying to access the platform. Different results depending on the context (clinicians, research, etc.)
- For GP, the UI could inform to consult (or send the patient to) a Cardiologist if the models suggest (exhibits a higher risk

7. USE OF CVDLINK TOOL IN RESEARCH

It has been recognized that using health data also in federated way requires case-specific approval. E.g. utilizing certain biobank data for training a model for new purpose requires new approval. Is this always the case (except for publicly available datasets)?

- Generally specific permission per use case is needed. There may be exceptions in some countries.
- Dependent on the case specific approval of the data, there should be measures in place to prevent unauthorized use of data. There may need be an expiry date.
- Yes, it is necessary (except if the data could be anonymized – here it is important to understand the target group, this gives the required specifications for the process of anonymization)

How could the approval process be made easier? Could there be joint/automated approval process facilitated by CVDLINK or does the user need to apply separately for each dataset?

- Ideally requests handled centrally through CVDLINK. Otherwise, the user would likely not go through all the country/dataset specific request.

- Having a pre-filled approval form would be helpful. This could include what is usually contained in a data processing agreement. This could be managed centrally, like a CVDLINK back office but this would require staffing etc
- Establish a list of (European) preapproved partners/stakeholders who can be approved more easily/faster - if you get access to one database once, you are 'preapproved' when requesting a second one (linked to a rating for an organisation)

8. SUPPORTED AI/ML MODEL TYPES

What types of models should the CVDLINK be able to create?

- Depending on the data type – if data takes into consideration more sophisticated factors this requires a more sophisticated model (i.e., neural networks rather than decision trees).
- In general, we should be looking at multimodal models as a final goal. Not sure if we'll be able to reach that, but models that fuse information from different data types would be best.
- Even now, a lot of the data we're looking at have a lot of metadata that can be used. A model that can analyze these layers is needed
- Models where false negatives are very uncommon
- Clustering, feature selection, XAI-models

Is there a need for deep learning algorithms?

- Absolutely. Traditional ML models cannot handle big amount of heterogenic/complex data
- For imaging, it has been demonstrated that deep learning algorithms extract much more information than traditional AI multimodal models where you manually extract characteristics. So, yes
- An important thing here is that decision trees are much easier to interpret - Decision tree is explainable method but lacks capacity. Decision trees are less likely used for cardiology
- Feature extraction would need to be created to aid explainability
- Recurrent neural networks (RNN) are not recommended

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